

THE ROLE OF PRACTICAL EXERCISES IN TEACHING TECHNICAL DISCIPLINES

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Abstract: Three articles describe the forms and methods of organizing practical training. Development of recommendations on traditional teaching methods in the organization of practical training.

Key words: Practical training, Science and technology, organization of education are produced.

Introduction:

Deep learning of lecture materials, organization of practical exercises to be able to apply the learned pedagogical information in practice. Practical training is a form of training that directs educators to engage in conversation with learners, provides conditions for the implementation of theoretical knowledge in practical activities.

Practical training classes can be divided into two types. These are practical exercises from subjects with lectures and non-lectures (*for example, foreign languages*). Implementation of practical training classes in strict accordance with subject programs and work programs and calendar thematic plans. A list of literature on conducting practical training is necessary. In the practical classes, where there are lectures, the use of the materials learned in the lectures is mainly reinforced.

The unique aspect of the practical training is that it is characterized by the educational process of the academic tasks, the organization of the activities of the teacher and the student, and the fact that the practical training helps on a practical and very narrow basis. It is mainly to improve the quality and mastery of the student's independent work for deep and thorough study of the knowledge acquired in lectures and practical training.

The progress of science and technology requires a new approach to the educational process, the use of active methods and technologies of education, because the method of giving power to the memory also increases the thinking and cognitive activity of the learners. The pedagogues of our republic are faced with the issue of not only imparting ready-to-learn knowledge, but also inculcating independent thinking, creative research, activity and ingenuity.

The term "*organization of practical training*" refers to specially organized activities of the teacher and the students, which take place in the specified mode. One or another organizational form of teaching, the combination of collective and individual teaching in various forms, different levels of independence of learners in teaching, different types of guidance of the teacher to the learning of learners appearance is described by methods. Adjusting the organization of training depends on the content and methods of educational work and support with educational tools. The organization of education is a historically existing, stable and logically completed view of the organization of the pedagogical process, which is characterized by regularity and integrity, self-development, personal and active features, and the constancy of the composition of participants. , the specified order of transfer is characteristic. It refers to the organizational form of education in the form of an organization of cooperative activities of the participants of the educational process (*educators and learners*) in the implementation of certain processes.

To understand the ways of organizing a team of students for the educational and production process, which is the organizational direction of teaching specialty subjects, how to lead, initiate, and structure educational activities.

When choosing one or another form of education, in the process of arming students with professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, the main factors (*indicators*) that determine their absolute goal and immediate tasks, content and methods, as well as material conditions, are related to one or another form.

Teachers of specialized subjects use the knowledge and skills that students have acquired during theoretical training and deepen them when conducting practical training in specialized subjects. The intended purpose of practical training largely determines the methodology of conducting it, the methods of the teacher of a special subject to guide the work of students, the procedure for performing some experimental or practical work, and so on. After the students have mastered the theoretical material and become familiar with the studied phenomena and processes, it is much easier to conduct practical training with them. In this case, the teacher's training information on a new topic will be very short and clear. It is considered more complicated to perform practical exercises, where students have to make certain conclusions based on the results, and it is necessary to prepare students for this in advance and the teacher's educational information should be more detailed.

The teacher leads the students by giving instructions on the process of practical training. The main goal of instruction is to create the basis of the direction of activity for the most effective performance of the task in the minds of students. Psychologists' studies show that human labor has two aspects: orientation and performance aspects. The direction side is the reflection of the objective conditions of the activity (*issues, methods, criteria, performance conditions, technical means, etc.*) in the human psyche, and the execution side is the direct execution of the action. According to the teachings of I. P. Pavlov, the directional reflex is the basis for the formation of conditional connections in the central nervous system. These connections are the physiological basis of the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities. A system of guidelines is used in the implementation of practical training in the educational process. Introductory, current and final instructions according to the time of the training; according to the method of providing information, it is divided into oral and written instructions. Introductory instructions are very important in preparing students for practical training. Each experimental-practical exercise will give positive and valuable results only if the goals and paths leading to the goal are clear to the students. Students need to understand how the proposed work is related to the material studied or how it is important for further progress. The methodology of the introductory instruction depends to a large extent on the main didactic purpose of conducting the practical training and how it is conducted.

Another form of teaching used in the teaching of specialized subjects is practical training. If the lecture is held in a large group, the practical training is considered a form of educational work conducted in a separate group, and students are encouraged to engage in educational activities, independent learning, and creative thinking. is a form of learning. That is why it is a unique form of teaching in a higher education school.

Practical (*Latin amaliium*) was the first form of discussion of information by scientists in a specific scientific field. Later, moving from scientific activities to the educational process, it became a form of determining students' diligence, level of knowledge, interest in science, character, psychology, and now practical training is in the form of conversation, exchange of ideas on lectures, role-playing games. transfer is provided.

The important part of the practical, lecture-based training is that both the teacher and the student are thoroughly prepared. Owners of both activities should familiarize themselves with the main and additional literature in order to

work with sources and find answers to the questions indicated in the practical plan.

Another important aspect of the practical training is that there is a live dialogue, a clash of conflicting ideas, and work to solve them according to the student's needs. That's why the practical teacher should clearly choose the ways of live communication with the audience, debates, proving his point of view, listening to the opinions of others, entering into discussions. At the end of the session, the teacher makes a general conclusion, notes the progress of the practical session, the activeness or passivity of the participants, makes recommendations about conducting the next practical session, thinks, and fills in the thoughts. It would be appropriate to ask questions, put forward issues, give advice, publish a list of literature.

If the practical training conducted at a high level in terms of scientific theory, practical and method, instills in students interest in science, enthusiasm for working with sources and literature, and a desire to be active, teachers can improve their scientific and theoretical qualifications and have a positive attitude towards scientific literature. Science fosters confidence in news and enthusiasm for solving problems posed to science. Therefore, the teacher's skills play an important role in the quality and effectiveness of practical training. Practical training has a unique educational and educational value. In it, students openly express their opinions and points of view, defend what they have learned, and exchange ideas in dialogue.

In order for practical training to be really interesting, it should be in the form of a debate, but it should be controlled. For this purpose, the order of the debate is thought out by the teacher in advance, certain questions, examples, plots are defined in the working plan.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the success of practical training always depends on the activity of students, therefore, the second duty of the teacher is to comprehensively develop practical training and motivate students. Student activity is not only practical participation and discussion, but also the process of developing listening skills. Therefore, important qualities such as listening and speaking skills should be explained to students.

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